

In the spectrum of the cobalt(II) complex four bands are observed at 8203(s), 10055(sh), 17310(sh) and 21012(s) cm^{-1} which are assigned⁵ to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)(\gamma_1)$; ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^2T_{1g}, {}^2T_{2g}(\gamma_2)$; ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)(\gamma_3)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)(\gamma_4)$ respectively. The shoulders may arise either due to the splitting of γ_3 in many components or because of the pseudoappearance of γ_2 transition⁶. In the transition ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ for weak field ligands, the term ${}^4T_{1g}(F)$ lies 6 Dq lower and the term ${}^4A_{2g}(F)$ lies 12 Dq higher than the ground term⁷, therefore the band corresponding to this transition is equal to 18 Dq, yielding the value of 10 Dq to be 9610 cm^{-1} and the value of B comes out to be 1001 cm^{-1} . The values of nephelauxetic ratio(β), γ_2/γ_1 and L.F.S.E. in the present Co(II) complex are calculated⁸ as 0.99, 1.92 and 16.45 KCal/mole respectively. The value of β suggests partial covalent character which is also responsible for the reduced magnetic moment of this complex.

The electronic spectra of the present Ni(II) complex consists of three spin-allowed bands due to d-d transitions appearing at 9882 $\text{cm}^{-1}(\gamma_1)$, 16380 $\text{cm}^{-1}(\gamma_2)$, 27025 $\text{cm}^{-1}(\gamma_3)$ and a weak shoulder due to spin-forbidden transition at 12050 $\text{cm}^{-1}(\gamma_4)$ are assigned^{7,9} to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$; ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$; ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^1E_g(D)$ respectively. The values of γ_2/γ_1 , L.F.S.E. in this Ni(II) DIMAGA complex come out to be 1.65, 1024, 0.943 and 34.38 K.Cal/mole respectively, revealing the octahedral symmetry.

A study and comparison of i. r. spectra of the free ligand-DIMAGA and its Co(II) and Ni(II) complexes, reveal the ligand as bidentate with ketonic-oxygen and imine-nitrogen as donor sites.

The sharp absorption bands appearing at 1685 and 1650 cm^{-1} (in free ligand) assigned to $\nu(>C=O)$ and $\nu(-CH=N-)$ respectively show the lowering ($\sim 30 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) in frequencies suggesting $\geq C-O \rightarrow M$ and $-CH=N \rightarrow M$ linkages¹⁰. In the far i. r. spectra of the present complexes, medium intensity bands observed at 320 and 340; 500; 520; 560 and 575 cm^{-1} in Co(II) and Ni(II) complexes respectively are assigned to $\nu(M-Cl)$, $\nu(M-N)$ and $\nu(M-O)$ respectively indicating the different bonds in the complexes.

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Studies on the use of Salicylanilide as a Spectrophotometric Reagent for Uranium (VI)

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THE spectrophotometric determination of uranium (VI) with salicylanilide has been described.

Experimental

Salicylanilide solution : A $4.65 \times 10^{-2} M$ (1%) Solution of recrystallised salicylanilide (BDH) was used.

Uranium (VI) solution : Uranyl nitrate (E-Merck) Solution in dilute nitric acid was standardised¹ and used.

Magnesium-EDTA solution : A 0.01 M solution was prepared from stock magnesium sulphate and $\text{Na}_2\text{-EDTA}$ solutions when required.

Spectrophotometer : A Higher-Watts H700 Uvispek Spectrophotometer with 1-Cm quartz cuvettes was used.

Procedure : Dilute the uranium(VI) (0.15-0.6 mg) solution to 10 ml, heat to 50° on a hot water-bath add 2 ml of the reagent dropwise and adjust the pH to 5.5-7.5 with aqueous pyridine (10%). Cool, transfer into a separatory funnel, wash the container with 5 ml water and extract the complex with 4 ml of isobutyl methol ketone. Separate layers and extract the water-layer twice with 4 ml and 2 ml of the solvent after adding 2 ml and 1 ml of the reagent. Combine the organic layers and dry with anhydrous sodium sulphate. Measure the absorbance within 1 hr at 360 mm against reagent blank.

Add 4 ml of the Mg-EDTA solution before adding the reagent for the first time when foreign metal ions are present.

The procedure is also applicable for uranium ores.

Results and Discussion

The λ_{max} of the uranium(VI)-salicylanilide complex was found to be 360 nm and Beer's law was valid for 1.5-60 mg/ml of the metal ion with the optimum concentration range of 25-45 mg/ml. The Sandell sensitivity was 2.8×10^{-2} mg of uranium (VI) per cm^2 while the molar absorptivity of the complex was $3870.9 \pm 3.06\%$.

The optimum pH range was 5.5 to 7.6 and a minimum of 50 mg of the reagent was required under the conditions of the experiment.

The relative standard deviation was observed to be $\pm 0.95\%$ in 38 determinations. Estimation of 40 mg/ml of uranium (VI) was possible in the presence of 0.2 mg of Ag(I), Tl(I), Co(II), Ni(II), Mn(II), Be(II), Fe(III), Cr(III), Bi(III), Ce(III), In (III), Zr (IV), V(V), W(VI) or Mo(VI) and 0.15 mg of Pb(II), Al(III), Th(IV) or Cr(VI) with relative error less than $\pm 2\%$ provided Mg-EDTA was used as the masking agent. Uranium content of several ores containing U_3O_8 between 2.29 to 24.70% was determined with a relative error within $\pm 1\%$.

Organic complexing acids, e.g. thioglycolic, tartaric, oxalic, citric and ascorbic acids as well as triethanolamine and fluoride interfered in the determination of uranium(VI).

The metal to ligand ratio of the complex was found to be 1 : 2².

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Potentiometric Studies of Complex Formation of Some Lanthanides with Methoxy Substituted Benzoic Acids

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MAY and Jones¹ have studied the interaction of Cu^{2+} with 4-methoxy benzoic acid in 50% dioxane-water medium. There is however no reference in literature on the work presented in this paper.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of Analar grade obtained either from Fluka (Switzerland) or E. Merck (India). Dioxane (E. Merck) was purified by the method described by Vogel². All the solutions

were prepared in water, distilled in an all glass apparatus.

The rare earth oxides obtained from the Bhaba Atomic Research Centre Bombay, (purity 99.9%) were converted to respective perchlorates and used in order to avoid the possibility of complex formation of metal ions with the anions. Their concentrations in solutions were determined by their estimation as oxalates.

An Elico pH meter model LI10 in conjunction with an Elico standard general purpose glass electrode and a saturated calomel electrode was used for the measurement of pH during the potentiometric titrations. The meter could read pH accurate to ± 0.02 pH unit. It was calibrated using standard solution prepared from buffer tablets supplied by BDH London.

Calvin-Bjerrum titration: The experimental procedure involved potentiometric titrations of carbonate free solutions of i) free $HClO_4$ ($5 \times 10^{-3}M$) ii) free $HClO_4$ ($5 \times 10^{-3}M$) + ligand ($2 \times 10^{-3}M$) and iii) free $HClO_4$ ($5 \times 10^{-3}M$) + ligand ($2 \times 10^{-3}M$) + metal ($4 \times 10^{-4}M$) against standard sodium hydroxide 0.4M at 30°. The ionic strength was maintained constant by addition of appropriate amount of $NaClO_4$ solution. An inert atmosphere was maintained inside the titration cell by bubbling nitrogen gas presaturated with solvent. The glass electrode was calibrated in mixed solvent (76% v/v dioxane-water medium) by method given by Van Uitert and Haas³.

Results and Discussion

The pK values of methoxy substituted benzoic acids in 76% dioxane-water v/v medium containing 0.1M $NaClO_4$ ionic strength, have been reported in our earlier communication.⁴ These are listed in Table I for ready reference.

The complex formation of lanthanide ions with different ligands was indicated by considerable displacement along the volume axis of metal complex titration curve with the respect to the reagent curve, at a pH value less than that of the hydrolysis of the lanthanide ion. The possibility of metal ion hydrolysis under experimental conditions was therefore,

TABLE - I THERMODYNAMIC PROTON LIGAND AND METAL LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF RARE EARTH CHELATES OF METHOXY SUBSTITUTED BENZOIC ACIDS

Ligand	Temp. = 30° ± 0.1° ; H ⁺	$\mu = 0.1 M (NaClO_4) ;$			Medium 76% : v/v. dioxane-water.			
		La ³⁺	Pr ³⁺	Nd ³⁺	Sm ³⁺	Gd ³⁺	Dy ³⁺	Bb ³⁺
2-methoxy B. A.	8.79	6.89	6.88	6.87	6.48	5.79	7.59	6.99
4-methoxy B. A.	9.11	6.80	7.22	6.86	6.21	6.03	7.51	6.93
2,3-dimethoxy B. A.	8.37	6.33	6.89	6.94	5.89	5.23	7.35	5.92
2,4-dimethoxy B. A.	9.29	7.10	7.63	7.32	6.88	5.83	7.78	7.15
2,6-dimethoxy B. A.	8.49	6.19	6.42	6.53	6.00	5.67	7.01	6.29
2,4,5-trimethoxy B. A.	9.33	7.30	7.16	7.33	6.62	5.81	7.72	7.66
2,4,6-trimethoxy B. A.	8.85	6.71	7.08	6.84	5.97	5.39	7.14	6.15